

Review

Comparison of Thermal-Fluid Cooling Systems in Internal Combustion Engines and Electric Vehicle Battery Thermal Management

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Abstract: Based on the mechanical of fluid and thermodynamics, this paper reviews on the thermal management systems of internal combustion engines (ICE) and electric vehicles (EV) by adopting a comparative method from four core dimensions including system configuration and cooling medium, thermal boundary layer development and flow regime characteristics, temperature uniformity and entropy generation law, as well as transient thermal response characteristics. The analysis shows that ICE cooling systems primarily rely on nucleate boiling and turbulent heat transfer, with the core objective of preventing local overheating and they have low thermal inertia and slow response. In contrast, EV cooling systems mainly use single-phase forced convection, with extremely stringent requirements for temperature uniformity and control accuracy, necessitating high thermal inertia and rapid response. This paper aims to provide theoretical reference for the integration and optimization design of thermal management technologies across different fields.

Keywords: *Electric vehicles, Internal combustion engine, Thermal management system, Temperature uniformity*

1. Introduction

With the global automotive industry's energy transition, the market share of electric vehicles continues to grow, and the thermal management issues of their core components are increasingly becoming a focus of research. Meanwhile, the internal combustion engine, which has been developed for over a century, has reached a highly mature and complex level of thermal management technology. Numerous existing studies have conducted optimization analyses on the fluid characteristics and heat transfer performance of ICE or EV thermal management systems separately. However, there is a lack of comprehensive and systematic comparative research on the two types of systems based on the basic theories of fluid mechanics and thermodynamics. This paper aims to fill this gap by thoroughly analyzing the fundamental differences between EV and ICE thermal management systems from multiple key physical perspectives, including cooling media and flow channel configurations, boundary layer development and flow regimes, temperature uniformity control objectives and the second law of thermodynamics analysis, and transient thermal response characteristics, as well as exploring their respective advantages, limitations, and the challenges and prospects that future electric vehicle thermal management will face.

2. Comparative Analysis of Thermal-Fluid Cooling Systems in ICE Engines and EVs

2.1 System Configuration, Coolant Properties, and Flow Direction

Both EVs and ICE are mainly indirect cooling. For ICE, coolant flows in the water jacket of the engine block and transfers heat through the wall [1]. Most mass-produced EVs, such as Ford and Tesla, are heat exchange through indirect contact with the battery cell through cold plates [2]. Nowadays, many electric racing cars use direct or immersion cooling, such as the McLaren Speedtail, whose battery is directly submerged in a dielectric fluid [3].

In indirect cooling, the cooling system mainly uses water-ethylene glycol (EGW) mixtures, such as 50% EGW solution [4]. The indirect cooling of the EV battery thermal management system is mainly single-phase forced convection. ICE is mainly nuclear boiling, that is, using the nuclear boiling phase change of the coolant on the high-temperature wall to absorb a large amount of heat. According to C. Roe et al., dielectric liquids used in direct cooling can be divided into single-phase, such as mineral oil; and two-phases, such as Novec 7000 [3]. The immersion two-phase cooling of EVs uses the latent heat of dielectric liquid to reach a higher heat transfer coefficient.

The cooling system of the ICE consists of a single main circuit and multiple parallel small circuits. In the main circuit, coolant enters the cylinder block and head from the water pump, and finally converges at the outlet. On this basis, multiple branches are connected in parallel to provide cooling for turbochargers [5]. The indirect cooling system of EVs usually has a separate closed liquid cooling circuit, which is usually coupled to the vehicle's air conditioning refrigeration circuit via a chiller to achieve active cooling [6]. Immersion cooling systems usually have no fixed flow channels and rely on bulk flow without forced flow direction [3].

2.2 Thermal Boundary Layer, Flow Regime, and Heat Transfer Coefficient

When a fluid flows over a solid surface, the velocity of the fluid immediately adjacent to the wall is zero due to fluid viscosity, resulting in a velocity gradient in the direction perpendicular to the wall. This thin layer with a sharply varying velocity gradient is defined as the boundary layer. The state of the boundary layer, including laminar or turbulent flow and whether flow separation occurs, directly determines the performance of the cooling system.

2.2.1 Comparison of Boundary Layer Development and Flow Regime

The ICE boundary layer initiates at the combustion chamber wall. During the compression process, the boundary layer thickness increases monotonically with the rise of piston moving velocity and reaches a maximum value of approximately 0.5 mm near the compression top dead center [7]. One main microscopic physical phenomenon is flame quenching, that is, when flame is extinguished by the cold wall, the unburned fuel and air will be directly discharged as Hydrocarbon exhaust emissions. The other is subcooled boiling of coolant caused by the excessively high temperature in the bridge zone of the cylinder head, which leads to local bubbling of the coolant before its temperature reaches 100°C. The generated bubbles grow and then detach from the wall surface [4]. In the thermal management system of EVs, the boundary layer starts from the air inlet or liquid inlet of the battery module and gradually thickens along the flow direction. There is an extremely thin layer of viscous bottom layer on the wall of the battery with a flow rate of almost 0, where the flow rate and temperature change is particularly large [8].

In terms of flow state, the ICE mainstream is highly transient, extremely complex turbulence, which is caused by piston motion. Laminar flow and turbulent flow can both exist in the mainstream battery thermal management systems of EVs. Turbulent flow is required for air cooling under high discharge rate (5C) conditions [8]. Temperature non-uniformity along the cooling flow direction is the core issue. The temperature of downstream batteries is significantly higher than that of upstream ones. Immersion liquid cooling can greatly mitigate this problem and operate effectively under laminar flow conditions with Reynolds numbers (Re) ranging from 126 to approximately 3000 [9].

2.2.2 Comparison of System Loop Architecture and Flow Path Design

When the flow velocity or Re changes, the heat transfer coefficient varies, which is usually

characterized by the Nusselt number (Nu) [10]. In the fully turbulent region, it basically satisfies the Dittus-Boelter empirical correlation: $Nu \propto Re^{0.8}$ [11]. It is not difficult to find that the heat transfer coefficient increases with the rise of flow velocity, while the growth rate gradually slows down. Therefore, this coefficient has a relatively low sensitivity to ICE cooling systems, but a high sensitivity to the laminar and transitional flow regions of EVs. Meanwhile, the pressure drop also changes with flow velocity and is characterized by the Darcy friction factor f [12]. A slight increase in flow velocity in the turbulent region will lead to a sharp rise in pump power consumption, so the design of ICE water pumps requires elaborate optimization. EVs show relatively low sensitivity in this regard; only when entering the turbulent region, such as in micro-fin channels, will the pressure drop increase nonlinearly and drastically [13]. In addition, for EVs, the Performance Evaluation Criterion (PEC) has a wide variation range and drops sharply as the load increases, so it can be used to quantify the heat transfer enhancement gain obtained per unit pump power consumption [14].

2.3 Temperature Uniformity and the Second Law of Thermodynamics

2.3.1 Differences in Temperature Uniformity Metrics and Design Targets

ICE materials, such as cast aluminum and gray cast iron, can withstand higher absolute temperatures, yet severe reciprocating thermal shock induces thermal fatigue and cracking. Therefore, uniformity of the temperature field is emphasized to avoid local overheating. The core parameters include the flow velocity uniformity of the coolant and the temperature distribution gradient of the cylinder head and cylinder liner. According to M. Liu, J. Lei, G. Song, and K. Liu, the coolant flow velocity in high heat load areas is generally required to be greater than 0.5 m/s [15]; the temperature at key positions such as the bridge zone of the cylinder head and the cylinder liner shall not exceed approximately 450 K [16].

For EVs, the optimal operating temperature window is narrow (25-50 °C) and a large temperature difference will lead to inconsistent electrochemical behavior, capacity fading, local lithium plating, and even thermal runaway [17]. Therefore, the maximum surface temperature difference of a single cell (ΔT_{max}) and the temperature difference between cells within a module (ΔT_{mod}) are two key parameters. It is generally regarded as an engineering standard that $\Delta T_{max} < 5^\circ\text{C}$, exceeding this threshold will cause approximately 10% capacity fading [18]. Meanwhile, the dimensionless non-uniformity index β can be used to quantify the distribution deviation of temperature, current density and heat generation rate simultaneously:

$$\beta_x = \frac{X_{max} - X_{min}}{X_{average}}$$

For instance, the β value of the temperature field is 7.5%, higher than that of the heat source (3.7%), indicating that heat conduction exacerbates non-uniformity [19].

2.3.2 Comparison of Entropy Generation and Available Energy Loss Caused by Temperature-Difference Heat Transfer

In the case of Entropy generation analysis starts from the second law of thermodynamics and is used to quantify the energy loss caused by heat transfer and flow, thereby balancing heat exchange performance and flow resistance loss. The heat source combustion temperature of the ICE cooling system is extremely high, so heat transfer entropy generation dominates. According to H. N. F. Feliciano, F. F. Rovai, and C. E. K. Mady, the theoretical ideal efficiency is 75% at 1200 K, while the actual efficiency is approximately 19–30% [20]. In EVs, the operating temperature of batteries or motors is low, on the contrary, complex flow channels will significantly increase flow resistance, making flow entropy generation account for a relatively

large proportion of the total entropy generation [21]. The theoretical efficiency can reach 97.8%, and the actual efficiency is about 35–51%, which depends on exergy loss [20]. Heat pumps and waste heat recovery systems can be adopted to reduce available energy loss [22].

According to Section 2.3.1, the main objective of temperature difference control for ICEs is to avoid overheating and maintain the stability of combustion and lubrication. For electric vehicles, it is essential to keep the battery temperature within the range to extend service life [23]. The Entropy Generation Minimization (EGM) method can be applied to optimize mass flow rate, channel geometry, thermal load and other parameters, thereby improving the thermo-hydraulic performance of the system. It is widely adopted in strategies to reduce entropy generation in low-temperature zones of electric vehicles, while internal combustion engines rely more on empirical formulas [17].

2.4 Transient Thermal Response and Thermal Inertia

The thermal time constant τ is the product of thermal capacitance C_{th} and thermal resistance R_{th} . It characterizes the inherent inertia of a system when resisting temperature changes or responding to variations in heat sources. The larger the time constant, the slower the temperature change, which means the greater the thermal inertia of the system.

2.4.1 Comparison of System Thermal Capacity and Time Constant

The specific heat capacity of the main metallic materials used in engines is relatively low. For instance, the specific heat capacity of aluminum alloy is approximately 900 J/(kg·K), and that of steel is about 460 J/(kg·K). In contrast, coolant has a much higher specific heat capacity; for example, EGW has a specific heat capacity of 3300 J/(kg·K) [24]. Similarly, battery materials also feature a relatively low specific heat capacity. Its equivalent heat capacity derives from the comprehensive heat storage capacity of all internal materials, including electrodes, electrolyte, separator and current collector. As an example, the specific heat capacity of Nickel-Cobalt-Manganese ternary (NCM) batteries is around 1100 J/(kg·K) [25].

In terms of time constant, ICEs have a small value and low thermal inertia. The temperature near the combustion chamber fluctuates drastically and rapidly in a periodic manner with the crankshaft angle. Macroscopically, the engine coolant temperature can reach a new steady state within tens of seconds to several minutes when operating conditions change. In contrast, EVs feature a large time constant and high thermal inertia. According to the experimental data from J. Zhang, under the US06 driving cycle, the change rates of the battery core temperature and surface temperature are relatively smooth [26].

2.4.2 Differences in Cooling Response Speed and Control Requirements under Transient Conditions

Sudden thermal load scenarios of ICEs are concentrated in transient operating conditions such as cold start, rapid acceleration, and heavy-load climbing [27]. Temperature changes can cause thermal expansion and alter the fit clearance between components, thereby leading to high thermal stress. For EVs, such scenarios mainly occur under operating conditions including rapid acceleration, high-rate discharge, and fast charging [28]. High C-rate discharge increases battery polarization and may trigger side reactions such as lithium precipitation and electrolyte decomposition [29].

For ICE vehicles, the main actuator of the cooling system is the wax thermostat, which features response delay, hysteresis characteristics and slow actuation speed. Even electronic thermostats require a response time of approximately 15 seconds [30]. This is because they

focus on coordinating the torque of power sources such as the engine and clutch, with the primary objectives of ensuring driving comfort and system efficiency, while having relatively low requirements for cooling precision [31]. In contrast, as stated in Section 2.3, EVs have a control objective highly concentrated on strictly confining battery temperature and temperature difference within a narrow safe range while pursuing low energy consumption [32]. Therefore, the cooling system actuator TEC adopts solid-state electronic cooling based on the Peltier effect, boasting an extremely fast response speed of only a few seconds [33].

2.5 Challenges and perspectives for EV Thermal Management

However, according to the research of Chang'an University, for electric vehicles, the uneven humidity distribution inside the battery pack will cause local high temperatures and performance differences among single cells, which in turn affect the overall service life and working performance of the battery pack [34]. Meanwhile, although the immersion cooling system has attracted extensive attention as an emerging technology, it still has many problems such as high cost, heavy weight and easy corrosion [35].

With the advent of the AI era, University College Dublin has proposed adopting advanced artificial intelligence and machine learning models such as Convolutional Neural Network-Long Short-Term Memory hybrid neural network to predict the temperature, heat dissipation demand and energy consumption of battery packs, so as to realize the dynamic and precise regulation of the speed of cooling fans or the flow rate of liquid cooling pumps [36]. This method can predict and cope with the future trend of climate warming and help mitigate global warming.

3. Conclusion

This paper conducts a comparative analysis of the differences in thermal management theories and management strategies between ICEs and EVs. From the perspective of the core characteristics of fluid mechanics, the in-cylinder flow of ICE is strongly transient and highly complex turbulence. In contrast, the battery thermal management system of EVs covers the range from laminar flow to turbulent flow. In terms of the core thermodynamic mechanism, the core control objective of ICEs is to avoid material thermal fatigue caused by local overheating. EVs impose stringent engineering requirements on the narrow-range temperature control. Finally, regarding transient response characteristics, ICEs feature low thermal inertia and obvious response lag of cooling system actuators, while EVs have high thermal inertia but impose extremely high requirements on the response speed and control accuracy of the cooling system. Based on the research findings of Chang'an University, current thermal management of EVs still faces challenges such as uneven humidity distribution inside battery packs, high costs of immersion cooling, and high susceptibility to corrosion. Meanwhile, the method proposed by University College Dublin, which adopts artificial intelligence and machine learning models, represents a cutting-edge core research direction for achieving balanced optimization of energy efficiency and temperature control performance in electric vehicle thermal management systems.

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